

INFESTATION LEVELS OF SUNN PEST (*EURYGASTER INTEGRICEPS* PUT.) AND CEREAL LEAF BEETLE (*OULEMA MELANOPUS* L.) IN AUTUMN WHEAT FIELDS

¹Alamuratov Rayimjon Abdimurot o'g'li., ²Bababekov Qaladar

^{1,2}Research Institute of Plant Quarantine and Protection, Tashkent Region

muslimarayimjonovna91@mail.com.

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Abstract: Monitoring of the Occurrence Level of *Eurygaster integriceps* and *Olema melanopus* in Autumn Wheat Fields of Sirdarya Region. In the farmlands of districts in Sirdarya region, monitoring was conducted to determine the occurrence level of the harmful pests *Eurygaster integriceps* and *Olema melanopus*, which pose a serious threat to crop yield in autumn wheat fields. The pest density per 0.25 m² area was assessed.

Keywords: Wheat, pest, chewing insect, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Olema melanopus*, larva, adult stage.

Резюме: Мониторинг степени появления вредителей *Eurygaster integriceps* и *Olema melanopus* на озимых пшеничных полях Сирдарьинской области. С целью определения степени распространения опасных вредителей, таких как *Eurygaster integriceps* и *Olema melanopus*, представляющих серьёзную угрозу урожайности, на приусадебных участках и полях озимой пшеницы в районах Сирдарьинской области был проведён мониторинг. Плотность вредителей оценивалась на площади 0,25 м².

Ключевые слова: пшеница, вредители, грызущие насекомые, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Olema melanopus*, личинка, взрослая стадия.

Anatasiya: Sirdaryo viloyatining kuzgi bug'doy dalalarida *Eurygaster integriceps* va *Olema melanopus*ning paydo bo'lish darajasi monitoringi. Sirdaryo viloyati tumanlari tomorqalarida kuzgi bug'doy maydonlarida hosildorlikka jiddiy xavf tug'diruvchi *Eurygaster integriceps* va *Olema melanopus* kabi zararli zararkunandalarning tarqalish darajasini aniqlash maqsadida monitoring o'tkazildi. 0,25 m² maydonga zararkunandalar zichligi baholandi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bug'doy, zararkunanda, kemiruvchi, *Eurygaster integriceps*, *Olema melanopus*, lichinka, imago bosqichi.

Introduction: Cereal crops rank first among the major agricultural products used for human nutrition worldwide, with wheat occupying the top position as the primary food source [4]. Owing to its adaptability to diverse climatic conditions, *Triticum spp.* is cultivated extensively across the globe and serves as a staple food for more than half of the world's population. Global wheat production is estimated at approximately 770 million tons [5].

Its significance as a major food crop grown in both irrigated and arid regions further highlights its value. However, various biotic and abiotic stress factors reduce wheat yield and quality and can sometimes lead to complete crop failure [7]. The varying climate conditions driven by global warming and climate change contribute to the emergence of abiotic stress factors in wheat. Additionally, certain periods witness the appearance or population surges of pests and pathogens that exceed economic damage thresholds [17].

In recent years, cereal leaf beetles (*Oulema melanopus*) and sunn pests (*Eurygaster integriceps*) have caused considerable damage to wheat yield [3;20]. In the absence of chemical treatments and other protective measures, sunn pests alone can lead to yield losses of up to 30% in barley and 50–100% in wheat [2;14]. The damage caused by *O. melanopus* has been documented in Syria, India, Pakistan, Iran, the USA, and Canada, resulting in yield losses of up to 55% in spring wheat and 23% in winter wheat [9]. Larvae cause more severe damage than adults and are reported to consume 1 to 10 times more plant biomass relative to their body weight [6].

To monitor the major pests threatening wheat productivity in our country, experiments were conducted in 2025 on winter wheat fields across three districts of the Sirdaryo region. These studies aimed to determine the incidence and density of cereal leaf beetles (*Oulema melanopus* L.) and sunn pests (*Eurygaster integriceps* Put). The methodology followed standard procedures as outlined by Golub V.B. et al. (1980), Dorokhova G.I. (1995), Polyakov I. et al. (1984), and Lowe (1984) [10;15;16;18;19].

During the tillering phase of wheat, observations along the borders and surrounding areas of wheat fields revealed that *Eurygaster integriceps* and *Oulema melanopus* had emerged from hibernation and began feeding on wild grass species of the Poaceae family located at field edges and nearby vegetation. In farms where the presence of sunn pest was confirmed, 20 samples (each measuring 0.25 m² or 50x50 cm) were collected, and the pest populations were counted and recorded.

1- figure. *Eurygaster integriceps* oviposition process.

2- figure. *Oulema melanopus*

Monitoring of Sunn Pest and Sawfly Infestation in Winter Wheat Fields of Sirdaryo Region, 2025. In Sirdaryo region, a total of 73,000 hectares were sown with winter wheat for the 2025 harvest. Pest distribution forecasting covered an area of 172,562 hectares, including 66,910 hectares predicted to be infested by *Eurygaster integriceps* and 37,237 hectares by *Oulema melanopus*. In April of this year, field trials were conducted to assess the distribution levels of these pests across the region (Table 1). In Khavast district, winter wheat was sown on 8,000 hectares. In the “Abdullabekov Abbas” farm located in the Farhod area, which covers 11.0 hectares, monitoring revealed *E. integriceps* larvae at a density of 1.2 individuals per 0.25 m² and *O. melanopus* larvae at 4.3 individuals. Similarly, in the “Elyor o‘g‘li Asilbek” farm (13.4 ha), the density was 1.3 individuals for *E. integriceps* and 4.6 for *O. melanopus* per 0.25 m².

In Boyovut district, 11,500 hectares were allocated for winter wheat cultivation. In the “Alp-Jamol” farm (7.0 ha) located in the G‘allakor area, 2.0 *E. integriceps* and 5.1 *O. melanopus* larvae per 0.25 m² were recorded. Meanwhile, in the “Zur Ziyokor” farm (9.2 ha) located in the Navbaxor area, 1.1 and 6.3 individuals per 0.25 m² of *E. integriceps* and *O. melanopus*, respectively, were identified (Figures 1 and 2).

In Oqoltin district, winter wheat was planted over 15,000 hectares. In the S. Siddiqov area, where a total of 1,015.1 hectares were planted, monitoring in the “Agro Oqoltin Ko‘rki” farm (5.1 ha) revealed 0.9 *E. integriceps* and 5.1 *O. melanopus* individuals per 0.25 m². Similarly, in the “Ulug‘bek Shakin Sharof” farm (16.0 ha) located in the Andijon area, the same density of 0.9 and 5.1 individuals per 0.25 m² was found for *E. integriceps* and *O. melanopus*, respectively.

In Sardoba district, 12,000 hectares were sown with winter wheat. In the Paxtaobod area, where 948.4 hectares were under cultivation, the “Oqqayin” farm (9.1 ha) exhibited densities of 1.5 *E. integriceps* and 7.0 *O. melanopus* individuals per 0.25 m². In the “Qo‘shchinor Do‘stlik Yeri” farm (10.3 ha), located in the Qo‘shchinor area, monitoring showed 1.7 *E. integriceps* and 6.8 *O. melanopus* larvae per 0.25 m². Based on the results of the pest monitoring in the districts of Sirdaryo region, appropriate measures and timely implementation of chemical and biological control strategies were recommended to effectively mitigate the impact of these pests.

Table-1

Distribution of Sunn Pest (*Eurygaster integriceps*) and Sawfly (*Olema melanopus*) in winter wheat fields of farms across districts of Sirdaryo region, 2025.

T/r	Region	Districts	Areas	Farmer Enterprises	Land plot	Pest infestation density per 0.25 m ²	
						<i>E. integriceps</i>	<i>O. melanopus</i>
1.	Sirdaryo	Xovos	Farxod	Abdullabekov Abbos	11,0	1,2	4,3
				Elyor o'li Asilbek	13,4	1,3	4,6
		Boyovut	G' allakor	Alp-Jamol	7,0	2,0	5,1
				Navbahor xududi	Zur ziyokor	9,2	1,1
		Oqoltin	S.Siddiqov	Agro Oqoltin ko'rki	5,1	2,7	4,8
				Andijon	Ulug'bek Shakin Sharof	16,0	0,9
		Sardoba	Paxtaobod	Oqqayin	9,1	1,5	7,0
				Qo' shchin or	Qo'shchinor do'stlik yeri	10,3	1,7

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